

**DX \equiv Digital
Transformation**

DX \supset IT

Brain Odyssey vs AI Machine Learning, Language Education, and the Future of Humanity

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Brain Odyssey: How does brain work?

animal cell

plant cell

The basic unit of all living things is 'cell'!

Cells have different shapes depending on the role they play, but roughly they look like this. **The basic unit of the brain and nervous system is also a cell.** But it looks like this.

Nerve Cells in Brain

Source: YouTube

Neurons

Latin word for rope or tendon.

As Santiago Ramón y Cajal thought, Neurons are a kind of biological electrical wire that transmits electrical signals.

Neurons are nerve cells optimized for information transfer.

Generic Neurotransmitter System

Source: YouTube

Brain Odyssey: How does brain work?

The brain

Frontal Lobe

- Planning actions
- Learning New tasks
- Motivation
- Behaviour regulation

Temporal Lobe

- Memory functions
- Word based memory (dominant)
- Visual Memory (non-dominant)

Cerebellum

- Coordination
- Balance
- Equilibrium
- Muscle tone

Parietal Lobe

- Taste, temperature, pain
- Understanding language
- Auditory & visual memory
- Calculations
- Reading & writing
- Spatial awareness

Occipital Lobe

- Visual Perception
- Colour recognition

Brain Stem

- Breathing
- Blood Pressure
- Digestion
- Heart Rate
- Other Autonomic Functions

Stroke Helpline 0303 3033 300
stroke.org.uk

Source: <https://blog.naver.com/>

Brain Odyssey: How does brain work?

Reticular Theory (Neural Network Theory) vs Neuron Theory

"The brain is not a collection of individual cells such as neurons, but a network structure entangled like a net."
-- by Camilo Golgi

"The basic unit making up the brain is neurons"
-- by Santiago Rammon y Cajal

The basic unit of the brain is the neuron, and the brain is a network of neurons.

Outline

1. Brain Odyssey: How does brain work? (Nerve Cells in Brain)
2. **Neural networks in Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL)**
3. Debates on AI, ML and Human's Future
Ex) ChatGPT, Language ? AI : Human;
4. Conclusions (with why at AUT?)

Neural networks in ML and DL

(Machine Learning, Deep Learning)

Deep Neural Network

Deep network architecture with multiple layers (Layers in NNs)

Deep Learning (= Multiple Hidden Layers)

Activation function

Source: <https://medium.com/analytics>

Nerve cells (neurons)

Activation Functions

- If the inputs are large enough, the activation function "fires", o/w it does nothing.
- operate like a gate that checks that an incoming value is greater than a critical number.

Ex)

Sigmoid function

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

$\tanh x$ or $\operatorname{arctanh} x$ or ReLU

Battle in AI

The race to develop AI ChatGPT is unfolding into a three-way battle:

Google vs **Open AI** vs the **'AI Alliance'**

Meta(LLaMA-2)/IBM, etc.

OpenAI and OpenAI Global, Microsoft

"highly autonomous systems that outperform humans at most economically valuable work".

'Gemini nano/pro/ultra' (based on LLM) added to 'Bard'

Source: Getty Image Bank

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Debates on AI, ML and Human's Future

Source: YouTube

Jack Ma & Elon Musk hold debate, 2019

- AI is going to open a new chapter of the society
- Man can never make another man
- **Computer has chips vs Men have the heart**
- It's the **heart** where the **wisdom** comes from
- Computers **clever** vs Human beings much **smarter**.
- **Knowledge-driven** vs **experience-driven**
- We can definitely make **things smarter than ourselves**
- Computers are already smarter than people on so many dimensions
- We just keep moving the goal posts (AlphaGo)
- Trying to play a Computer Go is **like trying to fight Zeus**
- **We'll be far, far surpassed in every single way, guaranteed**

Weak AI vs Strong AI

Language ? Human : AI ;

Language is the house of Being

– Martin Heidegger

Language involves infinite use of finite means.

The mind comprises an extensive cluster of innate “modules,” one of which is language.– Noam Chomsky

Human **conceptual and linguistic creativity**

- involves several mental faculties; and
- entails **the existence of some kind of mental organization.**
- I.e., depends on perceptual-articulatory systems & conceptual-intentional systems, of course, but on many others too, like vision

According to Chomsky,
the mind comprises an extensive cluster of innate “modules,” one of which is language.

“What Is History?” Civilization and Culture – Edward Hallett Carr

↑
AI, ChatGPT

↑
Language

AI is just a tool and humans will be better off

Chomsky said that the characteristic of the human brain is its **ability to reason** based on available information and reach **new and insightful conclusions**. Further, the human brain is designed **to create explanations, not to infer random correlations**.

"We have to be able to say

- **not just** explanations and predictions,
- **but also** what is true, what was true, what might be true and what might not be true
- "which is the element of explanation and the mark of **true intelligence**."

"AI primarily capable of description/explanation, but **NOT conditional guesses or causal explanations**."

For example, if you enter information such as 'the Earth is flat' and 'the Earth is round', the information is designed to be given equal weight. This means that 'information processing' is handled so that the probability of receiving 'flat' and 'round' answers changes according to statistical results over time.

"Programs like ChatGPT

- **cannot distinguish between what is possible and what is impossible by design,** and as a result,
- **"ML systems' predictions are always superficial and uncertain.**
- "Even if the prediction is correct, it is nothing more than pseudoscience."

In particular,

- AI can reproduce the 'banality of evil' because it **lacks morality and rational thinking**.
- AI is **indifferent to reality and truth** and only performs the actions specified in its programming.

The technique summarizes standard arguments by a kind of super autocomplete, takes no position, appeals to a lack of intelligence rather than simple ignorance, and ultimately shifts the blame to its creators with the excuse that they were 'just following orders'. "I do it," he explained.

ChatGPT's answers acknowledging its ignorance as examples, "we can't help but cry and laugh at their popularity as it is a fake scientific system **without moral concepts and linguistic abilities**."

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Conclusions: Language and AI for Human

- ✓ **Language is more than just a communication tool**
- ✓ AI will become one of major sources of value addition for the next generations in the future
- ✓ Develop AI or
Nurture talents who can better utilize AI
- ✓ **AI processes information that already exists, while human creates that information**

Weak AI vs Strong AI

Education should provide opportunities for self-accomplishment. At its best, **education** can provide a rich and challenging environment in which individuals can explore in their own way

Why at AUT?

➤ **3+1 program**

- Three years at AUT and One year at Korean AU
- New departments (Korean, English, IT Business)

➤ **4+0 program**

- Four years at AUT and Zero year at Korean AU
- Engineering departments (Architecture, Civil & Construction, ECE)

✓ **Korean Diploma & Uzbekistan Diploma**

- ✓ Exchange Student Program as **optional**
- ✓ High Quality Education as **mandatory**
- ✓ **Major in technology** and engineering while **speaking in English**
→ high demand in other countries and UZ
- ✓ **Graduate school** in Korea or other countries, and then **come back to UZ**
- ✓ Enable AUT students to **fly higher and go further**

Why not for your high-school students at AUT?

Bio

- (URL) [Google Scholar](#)

- (URL) [Patents](#)

Myeong-Eun Hwang, PhD, D.Sc, Prof.

Education

- Electronics, Hanyang Univ., Seoul, KR (BS, 1992)
- EEE, KAIST, Daejeon, KR (MS, 1996)
- ECE, Purdue Univ., IN, USA (Ph.D, 2007)

Publication

- 15+ journals and proceedings
- 15+ patents in multiple countries

Main Activities

- IEEE SM / Member
- IEEE ISCAS Reviewer
- ACM/IEEE DATE Reviewer
- IEEE TCAS-I/II, TED, JSSC Reviewer

Career (19.5 years of professional experience)

- 2016.04 SK Hynix Memory Solutions, CA, USA (Fellow, VP)
- 2010.10 Samsung Electronics, Korea (Principal Engineer, PL)
 - Developed Enterprise SSD Controllers
 - Developed low-power design methodology under process and temperature variation
- 2008.03 Intel Corp., OR, USA (R&D Circuit Designer)
 - Designed Main Stream Microprocessors
 - Developed WSM and HSW (i3/i5/i7)
 - Two Spontaneous Research Awards, and one Kudo Award
- 2004.07 Qualcomm Inc., CA, USA (Intern)
 - Circuit performance estimation in nanometer technology
- 1996.06 LG Semiconductor, Korea (R&D, Senior Engineer)
 - Designed Various Micro-Controller Units (MCUs)
 - Designed i8051 compatible high speed MCU architecture
 - Designed MPACT Media Processor
 - Designed TMS320C54X compatible DSP Processors

Questions?

One is only micrometers wide. The other is billions of light-years across. One shows neurons in a mouse brain. The other is a simulated image of the universe. Together they suggest the surprisingly similar patterns found in vastly different natural phenomena. DAVID CONSTANTINE

Mark Miller

Mark Miller, a doctoral student at Brandeis University, is researching how particular types of neurons in the brain are connected to one another. By staining thin slices of a mouse's brain, he can identify the connections visually. The image above shows three neuron cells on the left (two red and one yellow) and their connections.

Source: Mark Miller, Brandeis University; Virgo Consortium for Cosmological Supercomputer Simulations; www.visualcomplexity.com

Virgo Consortium

An international group of astrophysicists used a computer simulation last year to recreate how the universe grew and evolved. The simulation image above is a snapshot of the present universe that features a large cluster of galaxies (bright yellow) surrounded by thousands of stars, galaxies and dark matter (web).

The New York Times

Source: Quora